

Comparative Analysis of a Passive Solar Still with Different Fins Configuration

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Abstract: The use of solar desalination techniques is essential for obtaining pure water, a critical need in addressing the global water scarcity problem exacerbated by population growth. Traditional solar stills, however, often fail to produce sufficient quantities of distilled water, necessitating innovations to boost their productivity. The aim of this study is to explore the possibility of evaporation of water from solar stills with the help of heat-absorbing material fins into the basin surface. Conducted at Lakshmi Narain College of Technology, Bhopal, the research involved positioning the solar stills at a 23° tilt angle and compared with conventional solar stills with those modified using copper, aluminium, and iron fins. The findings reveal that the solar still equipped with copper fins significantly outperformed other models. Specifically, the copper fin-enhanced solar still demonstrated a productivity increase of 269.64% over the conventional design, when maintaining a basin water level of 4 cm. Over a 12-hour period, the copper fin solar still yielded 4140 ml of distilled water, in contrast to 3010 ml from the aluminium fin model, 2310 ml from the iron fin model, and 1120 ml from the unmodified solar still. These results underscore the potential of using copper fins to significantly improve solar desalination efficiency, offering a promising solution to enhance water production in areas facing severe water shortages.

Keyword: Solar still, Distilled water, Fin, Heat transfer coefficient, Basin.

I. Introduction

The demand of fresh water is increases as population increases. Our earths contains more water area than land area but it is inconceivable that only 3% of water is fresh water according to U.S. Geological Survey [1] and rest is salt water. According to this survey, from fresh water only 0.3% present on the earth surface which is accessible and rest of the fresh water present in the form of ice caps, glacier, ground water etc. To fulfil fresh water needs for earth population, convert salt water or unusable water to fresh water. Among desalination methods, solar distillation stands out as a promising approach to generating fresh-water. Utilizing solar stills, this process leverages the sun's energy to purify saltwater or other contaminated sources. Researchers have extensively investigated solar stills, reporting various advancements aimed at enhancing their productivity Authors are discussed on the working principles, performance, thermal storage materials, and configurations of collectors. In this work we discussed on the performance of heat energy transfer from fins to water. As we know the productivity of solar stills is very low. So, the researchers give their continuous effort on the enhancement of the solar stills productivity.

Humans rely on freshwater for survival. 97% water is present on the earth is salt water, and only 3% fresh water present on Earth [2,3]. Solar stills (SS) convert freshwater from saltwater and unclean water using solar energy[4,5]. Solar stills are: passive solar stills and active solar stills. Flat plate collectors, PVT, and electric heaters are the external device, employed in forced solar thermal devices, while natural solar thermal devices rely solely on natural resources (solar energy) for heating. Single- and double-slope solar stills are of passive and active in the solar energy

industry[5]. A single-slope solar still uses one glass cover on its slope, while a double-slope solar still employs two glass covers on its slopes. In recent years, solar water distillation systems have been the focus of research aimed at reducing energy consumption and fabrication costs, eco-friendly, and maximizing the water production and increase thermal efficiency

Kateshia et al. [6] studied the solar water distillation device with pin fin absorber using phase change material. They noted that phase change material with pin fin absorber, fresh water production enhanced by 30%. Experimental studied have been performed by Kaviti et al. [7] on double sloped solar still with conical fins attached on the water basin. They did energy and exergy analysis with different water levels and compared with conventional solar still. Maximum energy efficiency achieved with 1cm water depth and maximum exergy efficiency achieved with 3cm water depth. They noted that conical fins provides more the productivity than conventional solar still.

Kabeel et al. [8] economical study with various solar still has been made. Shmroukh and Ookawara [9] have been done experimental study on steeped solar still with copper fins. They mentioned that fresh water production improved by 123%.

Panchal et al. [10] noticed that solar stills with vertical fins and tapered fins increase the productivity. Ramadan et al. [11] analyzed the effect of fin parameters i.e., fin numbers, fin height and fin thickness. They found that fin height increases the water production of solar still but it becomes low with high fin thickness and number. Jani et al. [12] experimental study have been performed to study the effect of hollow circular and square cross section fin on solar still productivity and found that square cross section fin shows maximum fresh water output. Abdelgaied et al. [13] also

studied the solar still with hollow circular and square cross section fin. They used PCM under the absorber surface to increase the distillation time. They found that hollow square fins improve the fresh water productivity up to 33% and hollow circular fins up to 47.2%.

Kabeel et al. [14] studied the hollow round shaped fins with pyramid structure solar still attached on the inner surface of the base using phase change materials. They mentioned that hollow circular fins enhance the productivity by 43% and the use of PCM, water production increases compared to traditional pyramid structure solar still. Modi et al. [15] used the hollow circular fins on double sloped glass plate with single basin solar still. Hollow circular fins increase the absorption area which enhance the productivity.

Previous works explored various approaches, including water depth variation, inclination angles of condensing covers, and exergy analysis. Additionally, design and materials like SS with fins, concrete, sand, fiberglass, marble, and rubber have been studied for TESMs.

This work presents a novel approach by incorporating black matte-painted fins within the basin water. It conducts a comparative analysis of four cases: a conventional SS without fins, a still with black matte-painted copper fins, still with black matte-painted aluminium fins and still with black matte-painted iron fins.

II. Experimental Setup

The solar still is operated in four modes: conventional mode without any fins, solar still with copper fins, solar still with aluminium fins and solar still with iron fins. The experimental and schematic diagram of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1 (a) and 1 (b). The condensing cover angle is chosen at 23° (based on Bhopal City, 23.2599° N, 77.24° E). In accordance with a literature study, it was discovered that the authors have proposed that the latitude angle of Bhopal City, which is 23.2599° N, gives the maximum productivity throughout the year. The height of the lower side is kept at 0.13 meters, and the higher side is kept at 0.27 meters, respectively. The experimental setup is prepared in the workshop of the institute using the material that is available at the nearest local market. Firstly, the basin is made with fly wood and insulated by foam. After that a stainless-steel sheet of approximately 0.51mm is covered internally.

Fig.1. (a) Experimental setup, (b) Schematic diagram

2.1 Preparation of fins

Firstly, cut the all fin materials into 400mm×400mm plate size and fins are cut into 67mm pieces. Join all 67mm pieces in cross manner as shown in Fig. 2. Then, coated with black paint.

Fig. 2. Fin structure for SS basin

III. Instrumentation and uncertainty

At the experimental point, an accurate result must be needed, and for this, measuring instrument's uncertainty is needed. Solar radiation is measured by M-210 solarimeter, falling on the glass cover. The temperature of the glass cover (T_g), basin water (T_w), basin liner (T_{bl}), vapor (T_v), and atmosphere (T_a) is measured using a digital temperature meter with K-type thermocouples. The standard uncertainty is calculated as [16,17].

$$\text{Standard uncertainty } (\sigma_{un}) = a/\sqrt{3}$$

Where, 'a' is the accuracy of measuring instrument.

Table 1: Range, accuracy, and standard uncertainty for instruments used in the experiment [18]

Apparatuses	Range	Precisi on	Uncertaint y
Solarimeter – M – 140	0 – 1998 (W/m^2)	± 10%	±5.76 W/m^2
Distilled output Collector Bottle	0 – 4000 (mL)	± 5 mL	2.89 mL
Thermocouples – K Type	–50 – 110°C	± 1°C	± 0.57°C
Digital TDS meter (FK-T06)	0 – 9990 ppm	± 2%	± 1.155 ppm

IV. Methodology

The experiment was performed in the summer season at the Solar Energy Lab, located at Lakshmi Narain College of Technology, Bhopal (23.2599° N, 77.24° E), M.P., India. On the first day, the Solar Still was operated in conventional mode with a water depth of 4 cm and a tilt angle of 23°. In the next day, the experiment was operated with the use of copper fins inside the water basin. So the solar radiation also fell on the matte black surface of the water basin as well as on black fin surface at the equal depth of water. On the second day, Solar Still was operated with aluminium fins inside the water basin at the equal water depth. On the last day, the Solar Still was operated with iron fins inside the water basin at the same water depth and tilt angle. Fig. 3. shows the flow chart of the methodology used in the experiment.

Fig. 3. Flow chart of methodology used in the experiment

V. Thermal analysis

The inside surface of the glass cover and basin liner absorb heat from the basin's water and fluids, respectively. Internal transfer of heat occurs through the following processes: radiation, convection, and evaporation. Because of the buoyancy effect, the inner glass cover pulls water vapour from the water around it. The variation in temperature between the basin water and the glass cover causes this process to take place inside the solar still.

3.1 Convective heat transfer

The glass cover transfers convective heat to the base fluid's surface through water vapour, due to the temperature difference between the glass cover and the water.

The convective heat transfer (CHT) is calculated inside the solar still using the equation written below [19]:

$$Q_{c,w-gi} = h_{c,w-gi} A_w (T_w - T_{gi}) \tag{1}$$

Where, A_w – Area of basin water

T_w – Temperature of water

T_{gi} – Temperature of inner surface of glass cover

The convective CHT between the water surface and inner surface of the glass cover, denoted as $h_{c,w-gi}$, is calculated using the given expression[20]

$$h_{c,w-gi} = 0.884 \left[(T_w - T_{gi}) + \frac{(P_w - P_{gi})(T_w + 273)}{(268.9 \times 10^3) - P_w} \right]^{1/3} \tag{2}$$

Where, P_w – Partial vapor pressure on water surface

P_{gi} – Partial vapor pressure on inner surface of glass cover

3.2 Evaporative heat transfer

The relation can be used to obtain the evaporative CHT (it can be expressed as $h_{e,w-gi}$) [21]

$$h_{e,w-gi} = 0.01623 \times h_{c,w-gi} \left(\frac{P_w - RH \times P_{gi}}{T_w - T_{gi}} \right) \tag{3}$$

Where, RH – Relative humidity

VI. Result and Discussion

Fig. 4. shows the incident solar radiation variation with time, being exhibited over the glass cover of solar stills. The glass cover received maximum radiation at an inclination angle of 23° during all four days of experiments. The glass cover experiences a higher inclination angle towards the sun, causing the sun's rays to be more directly incident on it. As the solar radiation increases, the internal coefficient also increases. The four experimental days experienced almost constant solar radiation. As shown in Fig. 4, the peak solar radiation was observed at 1:00 p.m. The measurements indicated that the solar still with an aluminium fin received 1228 W/m², the iron fin model received 1191 W/m², the copper fin model received 1181 W/m², and the conventional still received 1187 W/m². Solar radiation increased steadily from 7:00 a.m. to 1:00 p.m., and then gradually decreased until 7:00 p.m.

Fig. 4. Solar radiation of four different models with time

Fig. 5. The hourly variation of convective CHT of all four models

The convective and evaporative CHT are shown in Figs. 5 and 6 for all four cases. It was noticed that the convective and evaporative coefficients of heat transfer reached maximum values of 2.5 W/m²°C and 52.19 W/m²°C, respectively, between 7:00 a.m. and 1:00 p.m. in the case of solar stills operated with copper fin. The maximum convective and evaporative coefficients of heat transfer are 2.14 W/m²°C and 43.59 W/m²°C respectively, between 7:00 a.m. and 1:00 p.m. in the case of solar stills operated with aluminium fin. The maximum convective and evaporative coefficients of heat transfer are 1.72 W/m²°C and 30 W/m²°C respectively, between 7:00 a.m. and 2:00 p.m. in the case of solar stills operated with iron fin. Solar still without fin shows maximum convective and evaporative coefficients of heat transfer is 1.42 W/m²°C and 24.59 W/m²°C respectively, between 7:00 a.m. and 1:00 p.m. in the case of solar stills operated without fin.

It was found that the solar still operated with copper fin, produced better output than the conventional model of solar still. Because of their high thermal conductivity, copper fin provides a better output than conventional solar stills. It was observed that the convective CHT with copper fin decreased sharply after 1:00 PM as shown in Fig. 5, compared to the other three cases. It is because the thermal conductivity is more than the aluminium and iron so it also release heat more rapidly compared to other. That's why the aluminium and iron slowly release heat due to their low thermal conductivity.

Fig. 6. The hourly variation of evaporative CHT of all four models

Fig. 7 illustrates that the solar still utilizing copper fins exhibited the highest productivity, exceeding the water production of solar stills fitted with aluminium fins, iron fins, and conventional designs. Over the 12-hour experimental period, the copper fin solar still produced the greatest yield, generating 4140 ml of distilled water. In comparison, the aluminium fin solar still produced 3010 ml, the iron fin model yielded 2310 ml, and the conventional solar still generated 1120 ml.

Fig.7. Variation of Productivity in case of all four models of solar still.

The solar still with copper fin receives more solar radiation and heats up faster, resulting in better productivity than the other solar still. It was found that during the sunlight, the solar still with metal fins (i.e., copper, aluminium and iron) in conventional mode provide a better distilled output as compared to the solar still without fin. This is happening because the black painted fins are received direct solar radiation and transferred the heat energy to the basin water, while in the case of conventional solar still without any fin takes more time to heat up. So, it was concluded that the water production of the solar still with black painted copper fin was outstanding during hours of sunshine.

VII. Conclusions:

The productivity of a single-slope passive solar still was examined with and without fin, and it was found that black painted copper fin gave excellent performances as compared to solar stills with aluminium fin, with iron fin and solar stills in conventional mode. The conclusions of the experimental work are as follows:

- Solar stills with copper fin have higher productivity than conventional solar stills or those with aluminium and iron fin.
- A solar still using copper fin increases productivity by 269.64% more than a conventional solar still and the other two, while a solar still with aluminium fin and with iron fin at a water level of 4 cm achieved less productivity but 168.75% and 106.25% more than a conventional solar still.
- The experiment was conducted during the winter season with four different modes (conventional mode, solar still with copper fin, solar still with aluminium fin and solar still with iron fin) at a water depth of 4 cm. It was found that the solar still with black painted copper fin performed better than the aluminium and iron based fin solar still and the conventional mode of solar still.
- The SS with copper fin, SS with aluminium fin and SS with iron fin obtained 76.05%, 50.7% and 11.27%

additional convective CHT, respectively, in comparison to the solar still in traditional mode.

- The SS with copper fin, SS with aluminium fin and SS with iron fin obtained 112.24%, 77.27% and 9.23% additional evaporative CHT, respectively, in comparison to the solar still in traditional mode.

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